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**SIYOSAT VA JAMIYAT FALSAFASI /
ФИЛОСОФИЯ ПОЛИТИКИ И ОБЩЕСТВА /
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**THEORETHICAL BASES OF THE OPTIMISATION OF THE
ACTIVITIES OF NON-GOVERNMENTAL ORGANIZATIONS IN
UZBEKISTAN**

Annotation. The article discusses the socio-philosophical study of the activities of non-governmental non-profit organizations in Uzbekistan, their role in the life of society, and their importance in improving legal culture. Non-governmental organizations have their place in the life of the society as a structure of special importance from the social, economic, legal and political point of view. In the conditions of Uzbekistan, the trends of improving the activities of non-governmental non-profit organizations, new stages of improving the worldview and legal culture of young people are being formed.

Keywords: society, non-governmental organizations, political parties, educational system, innovation, political culture, law, reform, legal culture.

**ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ОПТИМИЗАЦИИ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ
НЕПРАВИТЕЛЬСТВЕННЫХ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЙ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ**

Аннотация. В статье рассматривается социально-философское исследование деятельности негосударственных некоммерческих организаций в Узбекистане, их роли в жизни общества, их значения в повышении правовой культуры. Неправительственные организации занимают свое место в жизни общества как структура особой значимости с социальной, экономической, правовой и политической точки зрения. В условиях Узбекистана формируются тенденции совершенствования деятельности неправительственных некоммерческих организаций, новые этапы совершенствования мировоззрения и правовой культуры молодежи.

Ключевые слова: общество, неправительственные организации, политические партии, система образования, инновации, политическая культура, право, реформа, правовая культура.

O‘ZBEKISTONDAGI NODAVLAT NOTIJORAT TASHKILOTLAR FAOLIYATINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI

Annotatsiya. Maqolada O‘zbekistondagi nodavlat notijorat tashkilotlari faoliyati, jamiyat hayotidagi o‘rni, ularning huquqiy madaniyatni yuksaltirishdagi ahamiyatining ijtimoiy-falsafiy tahlili keltirilgan. Nodavlat-notijorat tashkilotlari jamiyat hayotida ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, huquqiy va siyosiy nuqtai-nazardan o‘ziga xos o‘ringa ega. O‘zbekiston sharoitida nodavlat notijorat tashkilotlari faoliyatining takomillashuvi, yoshlar huquqiy madaniyatini oshirishning yangi bosqichlarini yaratish jarayonlari sodir bo‘lmoqda.

Kalit so‘zlar: Jamiyat, nodavlat notijorat tashkilotlari, siyosiy partiyalar, ta’lim tizimi, innovatsiyalar, siyosiy madaniyat, huquq, islohot, huquqiy madaniyat.

INTRODUCTION

Today in Uzbekistan, concepts that clearly define the foundations of a legal democratic state and civil society and the place of non-governmental and non-profit organizations in social policy are being implemented. Non-profit organizations and other institutions of civil society operating in various spheres of social life in Uzbekistan are now becoming an important factor in the protection of democratic values, human rights and freedoms, as well as legal interests, citizens' realization of their potential, their social and political activity. and is creating conditions for increasing legal culture, helping to ensure the balance of interests in society.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In Uzbekistan, there is a need to study the role and importance of non-governmental non-profit organizations in the life of society from a socio-philosophical point of view. Using methods such as interrelatedness, objectivity, historicity, abstraction, systematic principles, analysis and synthesis, ideas aimed at improving the activities of non-governmental non-commercial organizations of our country were put forward.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

In Uzbekistan, the policy aimed at building civil society and strengthening its foundations has been implemented as an idea put forward since the first years of independence. We can see the practical implementation of this idea in the fact that the activity of non-governmental non-commercial organizations is given a wide opportunity. The adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Non-Governmental Non-Commercial Organizations" on April 14, 1999 served as a legal framework.

"A non-governmental non-profit organization is established to protect the rights and legal interests of individuals and legal entities, other democratic values, to achieve social, cultural and educational goals, to satisfy spiritual and other intangible needs, to carry out charitable activities and for other socially useful

purposes"¹. According to our national legislation, a non-governmental non-profit organization shall protect the rights and legal interests of individuals and legal entities, the protection of universal democratic values, the realization of social, cultural and educational goals, the satisfaction of spiritual and other intangible needs, and the implementation of charitable activities. the structure is determined for socially beneficial purposes.

The main goal of the development of non-governmental and public associations is to ensure and protect the balance between the interests of society members. Non-governmental non-profit organizations and public associations are civil institutions that are aimed at realizing the identity of citizens, self-management in social relations, voluntarily united and aiming to achieve a certain goal.

"It is known that in modern countries, the government influences individual citizens through social groups to which they belong. Because there should be a force that encourages social groups to unite and act. Of course, this force should be organized by their interests. Although the interests are expressed as the interests of individual social groups, the members of these groups are not only members of this group, but can also be members of other social groups at the same time. The reason for this is that each social layer itself is divided into several subgroups, which differ from each other in terms of qualifications, occupations, and other social characteristics. It can be seen from this that each member of the group can be a member of the first group at work, and a member of the second group in his free time [Vaxobov U. B., p. 108].

Different strata of the population, every citizen actively participates in the management of society, realizing their interests through certain non-governmental non-commercial organizations and public associations. All spheres of social relations in the life of society are covered by non-governmental organizations and various foundations.

"As an important result of the processes of globalization, there is a rapid expansion of the network of international non-governmental organizations, which in many ways help to activate the protection of basic human rights and freedoms in various areas of the world community. In the political reality of the modern world, the most important task of the world community is the need to create conditions for humanity to live as a society. Currently, the main participants of the globalization process, including the NGOs, are interconnected in the spheres of activity of countries that were not previously the object of international humanitarian policy [Ernazarov D.Z., 2021: 103-b.]. In our country, cooperation with international organizations, in particular, the activities of international non-governmental non-commercial organizations, have sufficient legal grounds.

"International non-governmental non-profit organizations operating in the Republic of Uzbekistan, representative offices and branches of international non-governmental non-profit organizations whose main organization is outside the

¹ The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Non-Governmental Non-Commercial Organizations // Bulletin of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 1999, No. 5, Article 115. lex.uz.

Republic of Uzbekistan and foreign non-governmental non-profit organizations, republican, interregional non-governmental non-profit organizations are registered with the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan "is held"².

In our country, the leading personnel in the implementation of the tasks assigned to them and in the consideration of appeals from individuals and legal entities, together with state bodies, civil society institutions, including non-governmental non-profit organizations, self-government bodies of citizens, mass media and other has been establishing mutual cooperation with public organizations. In this regard, effective cooperation has been established regarding the consideration of the appeals of individuals related to the provision of personal, social and economic rights of citizens together with institutions of civil society. appeals coming from low-income sections of the population are responsible for the republic-wide NGOs with regional systems along with the relevant state bodies.

In this sense, it is appropriate to quote the following words of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I. Karimov. "Civil institutions, non-governmental non-profit organizations are now becoming an important factor in the protection of democratic values, human rights and freedoms and legal interests, creating conditions for citizens to realize their potential, to increase their social, socio-economic activity and legal culture. helping to ensure the balance of interests in society"³. As the influence of such organizations increases and strengthens, the role of civil society institutions in our society is increasing. Because the formation of each person in the social environment, his ability and orientation to a specific field, his confidence, satisfaction with life, ensuring effective interaction between the society and the state, the mood of the people, the changes taking place in the country depends on the attitude.

In accordance with the joint decision of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Senate of the Oliy Majlis "On measures to strengthen the support of non-governmental non-profit organizations and other institutions of civil society", NGOs and civil society are to be organized under the Oliy Majlis. The establishment of the Community Fund to support other institutions is a proof of our opinion. By now, the number of non-governmental non-profit organizations in our country has exceeded 8,500. We can see that in 2015, the number of neighborhood and village citizens' assemblies was about 10,000.

Professor Jesus Gil Fuensente of the Autonomous University of Madrid expressed the following opinion: "The Uzbek people have rich experience in building harmonious social relations. One of the main tasks of civil society is explained by the existence of such relations. In addition, during the years of independence, a significant and solid legal framework was formed in your country, which allows for the development and strengthening of public institutions. Despite

² The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Non-Governmental Non-Commercial Organizations // Bulletin of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 1999, No. 5, Article 115. lex.uz.

³ Karimov I.A. The concept of further deepening of democratic reforms and development of civil society in our country. / Report at the joint meeting of the Legislative Chamber and the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan. November 13, 2010. "XXI Asr" newspaper.

the fact that modern Uzbekistan is a relatively young country, non-governmental non-profit organizations are actively working in the republic. Today, their number exceeds 8 thousand. Such organizations exist at all levels of society, and they perform an important task as a connecting chain between the state and society”⁴.

In our country, targeted programs that are currently being developed, which are part of our pre-election program, play an important role in solving issues related to human interests. These programs are aimed at ensuring further improvement of people's living standards and quality. For this purpose, the Government of our country, together with the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis and the Senate, and with the participation of public organizations and non-governmental organizations, are developing an Action Strategy for the further development of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021. [Mirziyoev Sh.M., 2016] These forward-looking plans are reflected in the Action Strategy and are being strengthened in practical terms in the Development Strategy. As a result of the reforms, the number of NGOs in Uzbekistan is increasing both qualitatively and quantitatively. It is worth noting that in foreign countries, political parties are not considered as civil society institutions, but as independent political institutions. In our national legislation, political parties are recognized as NGOs with great political power and authority. For Uzbekistan, the years of independence were a period of rapid formation and development of various civil society institutions, non-governmental non-profit organizations supported by all layers of our population.

"During the years of independent development, our Constitution is a solid foundation for the construction of a legal democratic state, a strong civil society, free market relations and an economy based on the priority of private property, a peaceful, prosperous and prosperous life for our people, and Uzbekistan's rightful place in the international arena. is serving. Our basic law created ample opportunities for the formation of non-governmental non-commercial organizations and political parties, which are part of civil society, and their free operation, and strengthened the main principles and rules of the electoral system. [Mirziyoev Sh.M., 2016] Today, non-governmental, non-profit organizations are emerging as a unique institution of modern civil society. The institutionalization of the field of non-governmental non-profit organizations is also reflected in the concepts of social and economic development of foreign countries. As the types and scales of social relations increase in society, there are many efforts by scientists to research and study them.

CONCLUSIONS

To date, representatives of the non-state sector operating in our country have also gained a lot of experience in the field of social services. NGOs in Uzbekistan have achieved the level of quantity and quality in the delivery of social services to the population. As a result, the activity of highly educated employees and

⁴ "Jahon" news agency. Uzbekistan's experience in civil society development was presented in Madrid December 29, 2015. www.jahonnews.uz.

specialists with many years of experience in NGOs and the improvement of the quality of work will serve to increase the theoretical and practical knowledge of the young generation. Determining the place of non-governmental and non-profit organizations in social policy in Uzbekistan and giving suggestions on improving social policy, as well as social functions of non-governmental and non-profit organizations, directions of activities aimed at meeting the various needs of citizens, non-governmental public organizations to the main institutions of civil society, the general population Non-governmental non-profit organizations and public associations, which unite around them, influence all systems and institutions of society, are important as a civil institution that serves to realize and manifest the identity of our people and nation.

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